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OPTIMIZATION OF CARDIOGENIC SHOCK TREATMENT

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ANNOTATION

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are the leading cause of death and disability worldwide, with ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) leading [6]. Despite such advances and the widespread introduction into clinical practice of many effective drugs, angioplasty and surgical treatment, CHD kills 17.3 million people annually, which is 30% of all deaths worldwide [7,10]. Scientific significance: in acute myocardial infarction with blinded cardiogenic shock (class IV acute heart failure) norepinephrine is reasonable. Norepinephrine does not cause proarrhythmic actions, shortens bed days and is more economically significant than other vasopressors.

Keywords: acute myocardial infarction, acute heart failure, vasopressor therapy.

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ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ КАРДИОГЕННОГО ШОКА

АННОТАЦИЯ

По данным Всемирной организации здравоохранения (ВОЗ), сердечно-сосудистые заболевания (ССЗ) являются ведущей причиной смерти и инвалидности во всем мире, при этом лидирует инфаркт миокарда (ИМ) с повышенным сегментом ST (NSTeMI) [6]. Несмотря на такие достижения и широкое внедрение в клиническую практику многих эффективных лекарств, ангиопластики и хирургического лечения, ССЗ ежегодно убивает 17,3 миллиона человек, что составляет 30% всех смертей во всем мире [7,10]. Научная навизна: при острым инфаркте миокарда осложненным кардиогенным шоком (острый сердечной недостаточностью IV класс) целесообразно применяют норэпиренфрин. Норэпинефрин не вызывает проаритмические действия, сокращает койка дней и увеличивает экономической значимостью чем други вазопрессоры.

Ключевые слова: острый инфаркт миокарда, острый сердечная недостаточность, вазопрессорная терапия.

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КАРДИОГЕН ШОК ДАВОСИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Жаҳон соғлиқни сақлаш ташкилотининг (ЖССТ) маълумотларига кўра, юрак-қон томир касалликлари (ЮҚТК) дунёда ўлим ва ногиронликнинг асосий сабаблари ҳисобланади, улар орасида ST сегмент кўтарилган миокард инфаркти (STкМИ) етакчи ўринни эгаллайди [6]. ЮҚТК даволашдаги кўплаб самарали дори воситаларини, ангиопластика ва хирургик даволаш усуллари клиник амалиётга кенг жорий этилиши каби ютуқларга эришилганлигига қарамай, ҳар йили 17,3 млн инсонни нобуд қилмоқда, айни пайтда бу дунёдаги барча ўлим сабабларининг 30%ини ташкил этади [7,10]. Илмий номи: кардиоген шок (ўткир ИВ тоифадаги юрак этишмовчилиги) билан асоратланган ўткир миокард инфарктида норепинерфин қўлланилаш мақсадга мувофиқ. Норепинерфин проаритмик таъсирга олиб келмайди, стационар кунларини қисқартиради ва бошқа вазопрессорларга қараганда иқтисодий қийматни оширади.

Калит сўзлар: ўткир миокард инфаркти, ўткир юрак этишмовчилиги ва вазопрессор терапия.

Introduction. This figure is projected to rise to 23.6 million by 2030. In the world, including in Uzbekistan, over the past two decades, there has been an increase in morbidity and mortality from cardiovascular pathology [3,8]. According to the American Heart Association, the incidence of primary myocardial infarction (MI) is 1,300,000 per year, and the recurrence rate of MI is 200,000 cases per year. Non-ST elevation myocardial infarction (NSTeMI) kills 15% of patients, with death occurring within an hour of symptom onset in half of the cases.

Today, despite the development of medicine and the rapid growth of the pharmaceutical industry, mortality from the most severe complications of coronary heart disease (CHD) with acute heart failure (AHF) remains high. Mortality after cardiogenic shock (CS) can range from 30% to 50%. Even after hospitalization, the mortality rate can reach 18% to 50% over the next 12 months. Mortality from AHF accounts for half of all deaths [2].

Several studies around the world have shown that these drugs provide only short-term improvement in symptoms and, given their high prevalence, do not reduce or even increase mortality. The reason for the increase in mortality is that these drugs have arrhythmogenic potential, excessive calcium influx into cardiomyocytes and increased myocardial oxygen demand [5,9]. According to the analysis of many registries of patients with CABG, this complication occurs with low left ventricular (LV) fraction and is associated with severe diastolic dysfunction [1].

Purpose: improvement of vasopressor therapy in myocardial infarction complicated by class IV AHF (CS) in a comparative aspect.

Materials and Methods In 2019-2020, 112 patients with AMI complicated by CABG were treated in the department of "cardiotherapeutic resuscitation" of the Bukhara branch of the RSEMP. Of these, 67 were men and 45 were women. To assess the effectiveness of norepinephrine and dopamine, patients were divided into 2 groups:

32 patients in group 1 were prescribed norepinephrine (norpine 0.2%-8 mg 4.0) intravenously as an infusion on an infusion pump 0.03-0.2 mcg/kg/min for 24 hours);

In 48 patients in the 2nd group, dopamine (dopamine 40 mg / ml - 4% - 5.0) was administered intravenously at an initial dose of 2-10 µg / kg / min. Within 24 hours were monitored - hemodynamic parameters (blood pressure (A / D), heart rate, pulse) were under control.

Entry criteria for patients included in the study: clinical manifestations of AMI, at least one of the following criteria: 1) ST-segment elevation of more than 2 mm in two or more chest leads or ST-segment elevation of more than 1 mm in standard leads; 2) Acute blockade of the left branch of

the Hiss bundle 3) Low systolic A / D with symptoms of shock, and the number of heart rates is more than 100 per minute.

The control group included 32 patients without signs of CABG. In this group, standard therapy was prescribed: nitrates, beta-blockers, angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors, statins, anticoagulants, antiplatelet agents, and, if indicated, diuretics and glucocorticosteroids.

Patients in groups 1-2 were not prescribed β -blockers and ACE inhibitors, since they further reduced kidney function in a state of shock. This group of patients was recommended anticoagulants, antiplatelet agents, statins, hormones and vasopressors. TLT was performed in 22 cases in patients with CABG.

All patients with MI complicated by AHF were divided into two main and control groups to achieve the stated goal. Of these, norepinephrine was used as vasopressor therapy in group 1 and dopamine infusion as vasopressor therapy in group 2. And as a control group, patients with a diagnosis of AHF II and III class were selected. In addition, etiopathogenetic factors leading to the development of AHF, as well as its risk factors, medical and social aspects that affect the quality of life of patients, were studied and comparatively analyzed.

All patients received antiplatelet agents, anticoagulants, statins, basic treatment containing vasopressor therapy, and, according to indications, glucocorticosteroids and diuretics were administered. TLT was performed in 29 (22 with CABG and 7 with patients in the control group) cases.

All patients underwent such examinations as general clinical examinations, electrocardiography, echocardiography, 24-hour Holter monitoring on the 1st day in the hospital and on the day of shock relief, daily monitoring of the electrocardiogram, and control of blood pressure and heart rate.

To identify factors associated with AHF, a comparative analysis of the demographic, clinical and laboratory characteristics of patients with signs of CABG based on the presence of heart failure symptoms was performed. To study risk factors in patients with AMI, a questionnaire of 25 questions was conducted. According to the questionnaire, patients with class IV AHF were older, often with CVD (hypertension, chronic heart failure), background diseases (type 2 diabetes mellitus, obesity), bad habits (smoking, alcohol) and more severe forms of CABG. Statistical data have shown that in patients with MI, the above risk factors are often found, that these pathologies are jointly complicated by varying degrees of AHF.

The obtained data were processed on a computer using a set of statistical programs. Among the patients examined for MI complicated by AHF class II and III, 3 patients (9.4%) had a history of diabetes mellitus, 22 patients (68.8%) hypercholesterolemia, 3 (9.4%) postinfarction cardiosclerosis, 6 patients (18.75%) had atrial fibrillation, 18 (56.3%) had hypertension and 30 (98.8%) suffered from anginal pain. The patients included 41 middle-aged people and 71 elderly people. When studying the anamnesis of patients diagnosed with MI complicated by class IV AHF, diabetes mellitus was detected in 34 patients (42.5%), postinfarction cardiosclerosis in 34 (42.5%), hypercholesterolemia in 27 (33.8%), atrial fibrillation in 12 (15%), metabolic syndrome in 50 patients (62.5%) and chronic heart failure of varying degrees in 74 (92.5%) patients. TLT was performed in 13 patients of the 1st group, 9 patients of the 2nd group and 7 patients of the control group. Patients with shock symptoms were more likely to be diagnosed in the elderly, diabetes mellitus, postinfarction cardiosclerosis and somatic diseases than in patients without shock symptoms. Patients diagnosed with shock were more reliably identified in the group with single, paired, group episodes of ventricular extrasystole and episodes of ventricular tachycardia than in the control group. All TLTs were performed in the hospital. There were no deaths during TLT. In patients who underwent TLT, the number of bed-days decreased by 2.3 ± 0.9 days compared with those who did not undergo TLT, clinical symptoms significantly changed after TLT, which was manifested by a decrease in patient complaints, a decrease in the ST segment on the ECG, and a decrease in the depth pathological Q wave. Perhaps this indicates a marked improvement in the restoration of blood circulation of the coronary blood flow. AMI recurrence was noted in 6 patients in the group diagnosed with CABG and in 2 patients in the control group.

On the first day in patients with signs of CABG, 11 patients (13.7%) went to the hospital, on the 2nd day - 26 (32.5%) and by the 3rd day 20 patients (25%) and 23 (28.7%) patients treated for more than >3 days.

Prior to infusion, the patient's QT interval variance was between readings (361.3 ± 16.7 ms). After infusion, the values were 314.3 ± 12.3 ms in the norepinephrine group and 323.6 ± 9.2 ms in the dopamine group. After norepinephrine infusion, the QT interval was significantly shortened compared with the dopamine group, which reduced the risk of arrhythmias ($t = 2.27$, $df = 115$, $p < 0.025$).

Due to the fact that norepinephrine did not increase myocardial oxygen demand, significant positive changes in segments were observed with it. Also, the effect of additional vasodilation improved blood circulation in the myocardium, which is very important in patients with AMI.

The index of global systolic function of the left ventricle when using norepinephrine showed a significant increase in ejection fraction (EF) from 46.8 ± 2.5 to $54.4 \pm 0.5\%$ ($t = 6.77$, $df = 50$, $p > 0.05$). According to the results of Holter monitoring in patients, the symptoms of ectopic activity in patients treated with norepinephrine subsequently significantly decreased. No arrhythmias were reported before or after infusion, depending on the nature and degree of statistical significance. Ventricular extrasystole (VE) was treated with amiodarone, a representative of class III antiarrhythmic drugs. Norepinephrine infusion was well received by all patients. The only side effect is headache. This was also quickly corrected with the help of analgesics.

Increased heart rate during dopamine infusion, in turn, increased myocardial oxygen demand (average 10 beats per minute, mean A/D 11 mm Hg), which was manifested by the expansion of the ischemic zone in 21 patients. In patients treated with dopamine, the dispersion of the QT interval exceeded 100 ms. Compared with the daily Holter monitoring of patients admitted to the hospital within 24 hours from the moment of admission and within 24 hours from the day of relief of CABG, PVCs and supraventricular arrhythmias were more often recorded in patients treated with dopamine than in the norepinephrine group. In patients treated with dopamine prior to infusion, EF was $48.4 \pm 3.6\%$ and end-diastolic index (EDR) was 5.5 cm. /kg/min in 6 patients, 6-10mcg/kg/min in 6 patients or more.

The mean number of days of hospital stay in CS patients was 8.5 ± 1.2 days in the norepinephrine group and 12.2 ± 1.3 days in the dopamine group ($t = 2.1$, $df = 78$, $p = 0.04$). Heart rhythm disturbances were less common in the 1st group compared to the 2nd group. Single, paired and group ventricular extrasystoles and episodes of ventricular tachycardia in patients of the 1st group were less common than in patients of the 2nd group.

In patients treated with dopamine, against the background of normosystole, there was a tendency to tachycardia. The increase in heart rate had unintended consequences for MI. This could lead to an expansion of its zone, an increase in myocardial oxygen demand and a negative change in clinical signs. Heart rate after dopamine infusion almost changed less: from $46.8 \pm 2.5\%$ before infusion to $49.7 \pm 2.1\%$ after infusion. Expansion of zones after infusion by echocardiography was observed in 21 patients.

The 112 patients who participated in the study were followed up during treatment. Of these, 80 patients underwent MI with AHF class IV, the average stay in the 1st group was 8.5 ± 1.2 days, in the 2nd group 12.2 ± 1.3 days, while in the control group (32 patients with acute myocardial infarction and acute heart failure class II-III) was 8.45 ± 1.5 days ($t = 2.1$, $df = 78$, $p = 0.04$). Patients of the 1st and 2nd groups were prescribed additional vasopressor therapy to standard therapy (anticoagulants, antiaggregants, nitrates, glucocorticosteroids, diuretics and thrombolytics).

Conclusions:

1. The most common clinical symptoms of MI complicated by class IV AHF are anginal pain (73.4%), shortness of breath (98.1%), palpitations (68.3%), discomfort in the heart area (43.7%). The main risk factors for heart failure in patients with AMI complicated by CABG were diabetes mellitus, postinfarction cardiosclerosis, advanced age and male sex.

2. Low doses of norepinephrine (0.03-0.12 mcg/kg/min) in the treatment of AMI complicated by class IV AHF increase blood pressure better than doses of dopamine (3-5 mcg/kg/min). It induces less resistance, resulting in reduced drug costs and increased cost-effectiveness.
3. With the use of norepinephrine, the end-diastolic volume of the left ventricle and the ejection fraction approach normal values relative to the dopamine group. However, the frequency of arrhythmias was 2 times lower when using norepinephrine compared with dopamine, norepinephrine increases blood pressure without increasing heart rate, does not increase oxygen demand, does not expand the ischemic zone. With AMI followed by AV blockade, it is advisable to use dopamine.
4. As a result of the use of vasopressor therapy in AMI complicated by cardiogenic shock, the number of bed days in patients decreased by 1.2 times, while bed days in patients receiving norepinephrine averaged 8.5 ± 1.2 days, and in patients treated with dopamine - 12.2 ± 1.3 days. Vasopressor therapy led to a decrease in mortality by 50%, while 3.6% in patients receiving norepinephrine and 1.8% in patients receiving dopamine, as well as drug consumption decreased by 1.4 times.

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